

EBFMC25-OP-35 · A Young Case with Stroke Secondary to Minor Trauma-Related Vertebral Artery Dissection

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Vertebral artery dissection is a rare but significant cause of posterior circulation ischemia in younger patients with stroke. The delay in the diagnosis and appropriate management may result in fatal outcome.

Case Presentation: In this case report, we presented a young woman who presented with headache and temporary loss of vision and diagnosed with left cerebellar infarction due to dissection of left vertebra artery.

Discussion: In patients presenting with clinical signs suggestive of vertebrobasilar system involvement, traumatic injury should be kept in mind even if the patient did not mention in the initial assessment.

Conclusion: In the differential diagnosis of younger patients with stroke, vertebral artery dissection should be suspected, and appropriate radiological evaluations should be planned for diagnosis.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Younger patient with stroke, trauma, vertebral artery dissection

INTRODUCTION

Young ischemic stroke is defined as ischemic stroke seen in individuals younger than 55 years. Cervical artery dissections are significant causes of stroke in younger individuals, involving carotid artery and vertebral artery dissections. The vertebral artery dissection is less common than carotid dissection. Etiology includes genetic disorders, trauma; however, it may occur spontaneously. Post-traumatic dissection can occur following major traumas as well as it may occur due to minor traumas such as simple physical activities, valsalva maneuver, cough or sneezing. The vertebral artery dissection is seen in younger patients when compared to carotid artery dissection, with incidence of 0.97: 100.000. It is thought that true incidence is higher as some cases are asymptomatic (Lee, Brown, Mandrekar, & Mokri, 2006). The vertebral artery dissections is a rare cause of stroke; and delayed diagnosis and treatment can result in mortality (Schievink, 2001).

CASE PRESENTATION

A 31-years old woman presented to emergency department with headache over 3 days; followed by loss of monocular vision over 15 minutes. In her history, it was found out that she had pain at head and neck region over a few days which she neglected but presented to emergency department due to onset of loss of vision. On diffusion MR imaging, multiple areas of infarct were detected at left cerebellar hemisphere. The patient was diagnosed as cerebrovascular stroke and admitted to neurology clinic. Again, in her history, it was found out that the patient experienced severe and persistent neck pain after sleeping with her child one week ago. It was also found that moderate headache persisted after the neck pain but did not affect her daily living, but she became concerned with onset of loss of vision. Based on her history, vertebral artery dissection was suspected in the patient. In addition, the patient had no history of chronic disease, hormone use, smoking or alcohol or substance use. She had family history of coronary artery disease. After initial assessment, the patient

underwent carotid-vertebral artery CT angiography which was inconclusive. Thus, the patient underwent carotid-vertebral artery MR angiography and fat-suppressed cervical MR imaging with suspected vertebral artery dissection. On MR imaging, there was narrowing vertebral artery lumen at V2 segment, false lumen sign and slow-flow. Anticoagulation was performed using warfarin with the diagnosis of vertebral artery dissection with extra-cranial involvement. After admission, no novel neurological deficit was observed with relief in head-neck pain. The patient underwent to identify etiology of young stroke and referred to another facility for DSA. Figure 1: A) Multiple areas of acute infarct at left cerebellar hemisphere on diffusion MR imaging; B) False lumen sign at V2 segment of left vertebral artery on T1-weighted low-noise, thin-slice cervical MR imaging.

DISCUSSION

Discussion: The cervical artery dissection accounts for 2% of all ischemic strokes and 10-25% of strokes inpatients younger than 55 years (young stroke). The cervical artery dissection are classified into two categories as carotid artery dissection and vertebral artery dissection (Goeggel Simonetti et al., 2015). Clinical presentation may be highly variable. Mild cases may be asymptomatic while it may be life-threatening in severe cases. Headache, neck pain, vertigo and dizziness are the most commonly reported findings. In addition, there may be tenderness at scalp, tinnitus or loss of vision. Acute stroke or transient ischemic attack are seen in patients diagnosed with highest risk for stroke within first two week after onset of dissection. Thus, dissection should be suspected in younger patients with stroke, particularly in the presence of headache and neck pain (Simon, Nassar, & Mohseni, 2017). Vertebral artery dissection may be either spontaneous or traumatic. In spontaneous form, dissection general occurs due to the weakened vessel wall caused by underlying vascular or connective tissue disorders. In addition, minor triggering factors may also be seen in spontaneous dissection. The degree of injury may range from irregular vascular wall, intracranial or extracranial bleeding to complete transection. Studies indicated that approximately 30-40% of carotid and vertebral artery dissections developed following a trauma. Although car accident- or sport-related injuries seem to be more commonly associated with dissection, minor traumas are more common reasons underlying dissections. Sneezing, blowing nose, weight lifting, sexual intercourse, yoga, fall and scuba diving as well as all mechanical events related to neck movements have been linked to cervical artery dissection (Engelter et al., 2013; Schievink, 2001; Simon, Nassar, & Mohseni, 2017). In arterial dissection, a hematoma is formed within the vessel wall due to tears at adventitia and intimal layer. The hematoma may lead narrowing or occlusion of the vessel or disrupt blood flow. A double-lumen sign called false lumen can be seen due to blood diffusion into vascular wall after formation of tears. The false lumen sign is highly helpful in the diagnosis on MR images (Schievink, 2001). The CT angiography (CTA) is the recommended imaging study in vertebral artery dissection. The CTA has sensitivity of 100% and specificity of 98% in the diagnosis. In recent years, upon advance in neurovascular imaging technology, high-resolution magnetic resonance imaging is being effectively used to show intimal flap and blood clot within an artery while T1-weighted images are used to show hyperintensity of vessel wall. Conventional angiography, which is gold standard in the diagnosis of vertebral artery dissection, is recommended in the presence of clinic suspicion when both CTA and MR imaging are negative (Fusco & Harrigan, 2011; Shakir et al., 2016). The treatment options may vary based on location of dissection, symptoms and degree of injury. Eligible patients presented within first 3 hours after symptom onset are assessed for systemic thrombolytic therapy. Thrombolysis via catheter angiography can be considered in ineligible patients who presented within first 4 or 5 hours. In patients who are ineligible for thrombolytic therapy, anticoagulation, anti-platelet therapy and endovascular or open surgical repair can be planned (Brommeland et al., 2018; Elder & Tuma, 2018; Yaguchi et al., 2019). In patients with vertebral dissection, it was reported that the risk for palsy and death were 24% and 8%, respectively. Poor prognostic factors include advanced age, bilateral involvement, arterial occlusion, insufficient collateral circulation, brainstem involvement and severe stroke at time of diagnosis. Prognosis is good in patients survived. Recovery without sequel was reported in 88% of patients (De Bray et al., 1997; Stahmer et al., 1997).

CONCLUSION

In young population, dissection should be kept in mind in cases presented with clinical signs suggestive of posterior circulation disorder even if suspected history is lacking and neuroradiological imaging studies should be performed rapidly to allow diagnosis and timely management.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no conflict of interest.

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